

E-Governance As A Tool For Rural Empowerment: Policy And Practice In The State Of Odisha

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Abstract

E-governance initiatives have emerged as transformative tools in the digital world, offering the potential to bridge the rural and urban divide and empower rural communities. The study explores the role of information and communication technology (ICT) in enhancing electronic governance or e-governance to deliver government services and promote rural Empowerment in Odisha. E-governance helps to exchange information and communication transactions, integration of various stand-alone systems and services between Government-to-Customer (G2C), Government-to-Business (G2B), Government-to-Government (G2G), as well as back office processes and interactions within the entire government framework. Through e-Governance, government services will be available to citizens conveniently, efficiently, and transparently. The study concludes that while ICT has catalysed progress in e-governance, sustained efforts in digital capacity building, rural infrastructure development, and policy integration are essential to realise its potential in rural Empowerment in Odisha.

Keywords: E-Governance, Rural Empowerment, Digital divide, ICT, G2C, G2B, G2G

I. Introduction

E-Governance has the potential to lead rural development through better service delivery, citizen empowerment, and government process transparency. Although issues such as digital literacy and infrastructure still exist, constant efforts are being made to fill those gaps and create more inclusive and sustainable development. Over the last few years, India has transformed its governance front by embracing Electronic Governance (E-Governance) initiatives. In developing nations like India, rural digital literacy levels are poor. Limited awareness about the advantages of E-governance poses significant challenges to implementation. The United States of America is the leading country in making initiatives in e-governance services, followed by Taiwan, India, the Netherlands, South Korea, and Malaysia. The adoption of e-governance in these countries followed "The Strategic Framework of e-government". This mode ensures the delivery of

individual services to citizens and two-way communication at each module. (Kumar Puneet, 2014) E-Governance in India is the seventh-largest country based on geographical area and the most populous country in 2025, with an estimated population of 1.46 billion (worldometer). 68% of India's total population resides in rural areas (Census data, 2011); lack of transportation, inadequate communication facilities, a lack of energy, bad economic conditions, health and hygiene issues, and cultural differences are still challenges in the development process. It is widely accepted that e-government is a vital tool for rural development. The Digital India Programme was launched by Prime Minister Narendra Modi in 2015. Its vision includes digital infrastructure as a utility to every citizen, NeGP(national e-governance plan), and e-Kranti(Electronic Delivery of services). Its vision is to transform e-governance to transform governance. The Government of India initiated an e-governance project in the late 1990s. The Union Government has approved a national e-governance plan (NeGp) comprising 27 Mission Mode Projects(MMPS), 9 Central (MMPS), 11 states (MMPS), and seven integrated MMPS to give a boost to e-governance initiatives in India. Department of Information Technology (DIT) and the Department of Administrative Reforms and Public Grievances (DAR) have formulated a National e-governance plan (NeGP) with the vision to "Make all public service accessible to the common man in his locality, through common service delivery outlets and ensure efficiency, transparency and reliability of such services at affordable costs to realize the basic needs of the common man" The second administrative Reform Commission(ARC) titled "Promoting e-governance-The smart way forward" identified the needs for e-governance to bring Government closer to its citizen(G2C). (Sahoo, 2016) The Indian Government introduced the concept of decentralized governance through the 73rd and 74th constitutional amendments, which encompassed the devolution of powers and functions up to the local level. The technical era in India has advanced information and communication technology (ICT), which has become a tool for communication. As a result, E-governance was launched by the Government of India's National E-governance Plan (Negp) on May 18, 2006, to enhance people's participation from the urban to the local level.

II. Research Objectives:

- To study the role of e-governance in rural Empowerment in the state of Odisha.
- To find out the various flagship e-governance initiatives project in Odisha.
- To study the opportunities and challenges associated with implementing e-governance in rural areas and to explore its future potential.

III. Methodology:

This study uses a qualitative research approach, utilizing secondary source of data analysis. Data are collected from books, research articles, journals, government reports, media sources, and official websites. This combined approach enables an in-depth understanding of how e-governance contributes to rural empowerment and governance service delivery in Odisha.

Iv. Review of Literature: The integration of information and communication into administrative processes has the potential to improve service delivery and enhance the efficiency of governance services. E-governance plays a crucial role in this transformation, though challenges such as the digital divide remain prominent at the national level in India, specifically in Odisha. **Sahoo (2014)** emphasizes appointing competent human capital to develop and maintain e-governance services effectively. The study "E-Governance at Angul, Gajapati & Puri" (**Odisha Secretariat**) discusses the challenges faced and strategies adopted to enhance public administration in the Angul, Gajapati, and Puri districts of Odisha. While initiatives like the establishment of Common Service Centres (CSCS) are commendable steps towards delivering citizen-centric services, there is a lack of precise accountability mechanisms to regulate their functioning at both district and state levels (**Sahoo Dipak, 2016**). To make Government-to-Citizen (G2C) services more competitive and effective, it is crucial to implement measures incorporating the latest technologies to promote SMART governance, i.e., moral, responsible, sensitive, and open governance. **Puneet Kumar (2014)** highlights the importance of raising awareness among citizens about the various services available through e-governance platforms. **Amutha D. (2022)** argues that rural development can only succeed if Panchayati Raj institutions have access to the necessary technological resources provided by the Government. The rise in digital literacy and technological advancements is leading and will continue to lead rural development in India into a new era of progress. **Nikita Yadav and V. P. Singh (2012)** provide a framework and application model of e-governance, listing various projects initiated by central and state governments. They also discuss the future of e-governance technologies and the potential for reducing labour costs through technology. Their research notes that although open-source e-governance solutions are popular in Western countries, such technologies are still emerging in India. **Singh Kuldeep (2012)** highlights that e-governance initiatives enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of administrative systems and establish mechanisms for information sharing vertically and horizontally within and outside administrative boundaries. These initiatives promote transparent, accountable, responsive, corruption-free, and citizen-centric services. **Nayak Satyajit (2017)** reviews various e-governance facilities provided by the Odisha government through websites and mobile applications designed to improve transparency, efficiency, and accessibility in public service delivery. The series of papers titled "Understanding E-Governance for Development" by Richard Heeks(2001) broadly discusses issues surrounding

information, knowledge, and communication systems in governmental processes. **Sharma Arpita (2013)** argues that a transition from 'open doors to open hearts' is feasible through ICT, which can foster open, transparent administration. For effective rural development, e-governance services must be citizen-centric and reliable. **Srivastava Vivek (2017)** analyses various e-governance programs aimed at developing rural India, identifying key factors influencing the implementation of e-governance facilities and their opportunities and challenges in advancing rural development.

v. Research Questions

- How do E-governance initiatives contribute to rural Empowerment in Odisha?
- How have the e-governance initiatives improved access to public services in the rural communities of the state of Odisha?
- What are the opportunities and challenges of e-governance in rural areas, and what is its future potential?

VI. The modules of e-governance

- Government to Citizens (G2C)
- Government to Government (G2G)
- Government to businessman (G2B)
- Government to Employees (G2E)

(Figure 1-E governance Module)

VII. E-Governance Initiative in Odisha

Odisha comprises 30 administrative districts; nine are considered tribal districts, and all districts have rural population's governance in Odisha. From time to time, the Odisha Government has taken appropriate steps and put the administrative and bureaucratic machinery to focus on citizen e-services. The Government of Odisha passed this landmark legislation, Odisha's Right to Public Services, through a transparent and time-bound process. Available data shows 13 services of Commerce and Transport, three services of Finance, three services of Fisheries and animal resources, two services of Health and family welfare, 1 of rural development, two services of the scheduled tribe and scheduled castes development, etc.

Out of this, other IT initiatives have been applied by various Departments under the e-governance programme, the e-districts project of the Revenue Department, the E-municipality project of the Housing and Urban Development Department, the SARATHI and BAHAN projects of the Transport Department, and the VATIS project of the Finance Department. Their primary function and service types categorize the following comprehensive overview of key e-governance projects currently operational in Odisha.

Table-1: Implemented E-governance projects in Odisha

Sl.No	E-governance project	Description	Types
1	Odisha One Portal	Unified citizen services portal for certificates, licenses, utility payments	G2C
2	Bhulekh Odisha	Digital land records system providing RoR (Record of Rights) and maps	G2C
3	Mo Sarkar	Governance feedback system through citizen calls after public service visits	G2C
4	Mo Seva Kendra	Physical centers offering digital access to government services in rural areas	G2C
5	e-District Odisha	Online platform for caste, income, residence certificates and public services	G2G
6	HRMS Odisha	Human Resource Management System for state government employees	G2G
7	IFMS Odisha (Integrated Finance)	Budget management, payroll, pension, treasury operations	G2C/G2G
8	e-Nijukti Portal	Employment portal for job seekers and employers in Odisha	G2C/G2B
9	Odisha Treasury Portal (iOTMS)	Tracks online treasury transactions, GPF, and pensioner details	G2C/G2G
10	Investor Facilitation Portal (Go PLUS)	GIS-based portal for land availability and industrial investment	G2B
11	GO SWIFT (Single Window)	Simplified clearance system for industries and business setup	G2B
12	Agrisnet Odisha	Farmer database and digital subsidy	G2C

		management	
13	e-Municipality Odisha	Urban local body services like property tax, birth/death certificates	G2C
14	Odisha School e-Governance App (OSSTA)	Monitoring school infrastructure, teacher attendance, and student records	G2G
15	Student Academic Management System (SAMS)	Admissions, e-counseling, and results for higher education	G2C
16	Odisha Rajya Rajaswa Bhawan Portal	Revenue department's services and document digitization	G2C/G2G
17	e-Procurement Odisha	Electronic tendering and procurement platform for govt. departments	G2B
18	Odisha Skill Development Authority (OSDA)	Skill registration, training, and placement tracking	G2C/G2B
19	Bhulekh Odisha	Digital initiatives for land record governance in Odisha are the Bhulekh portal, which provides real time access to record of rights (ROR) documents.	G2C
20	Common Services Centre (CSC)	Digital access points for public services, banking, telemedicine, etc.	G2C/G2B
21	Sahaj Portal	Unified integrated portal helps to achieve transparent and responsive governance for all.	G2C
22	Citizen Feedback and Grievances Redressal	It enables citizens to register grievances, lodge reminders or clarifications and access the status of their complaints in real-time.	G2C

(Source: Various websites)

VIII. E-governance for rural Empowerment

E-governance, the use of application of Information and communication Technologies (ICT) to deliver government services and promote participatory democracy, acts as a bridge between the Government and its rural and urban citizens, ensuring Simple, (SMART) governance stands for Moral, Accountable, Responsive and Transparent. E-governance is a public administration paradigm shift with digital technologies aiming to increase transparency, efficiency, and citizen-centric governance, focusing on citizen engagement. The most important features of e-governance play a decisive role in creating rural Empowerment, especially in socio-economically diverse areas like Odisha. The most important feature is accessibility, whereby e-governance platforms overcome geographical boundaries and enable rural citizens to access government services directly through digital means like web portals, mobile applications, and Common Service Centres (CSCs). Transparency and accountability are also important, enabling real-time monitoring of service delivery, digital audit trails, and grievance redressal systems like e- Abhijoga, thus minimizing discretionary power and bureaucratic secrecy. Platforms like e- Panchayat and PRI Management Systems enable decentralization and improvement in local governance, enabling Gram Panchayats to participate effectively in planning, budgeting, and implementation processes. Additionally, integration and interoperability between departments maximise service delivery and minimise redundancy, enabling rural citizens to access multiple services in a single digital window. The inclusivity in e-governance, especially with digital literacy and financial inclusion initiatives, enables marginalized sections like women, tribal people, and differently abled people to engage with governance platforms independently. Finally, the evidence-based policymaking capacity of e-governance enables targeted interventions in rural development based on real-time analytics and feedback systems. Overall, these features make e-governance a powerful tool to enable rural Empowerment in the form of participatory, inclusive, and efficient governance.

IX. Implementation Challenges:

The practical implementation of such initiatives encounters multifaceted challenges that impede their intended outcomes. The Lack of IT literacy and awareness among the rural and tribal people of Odisha, moving towards e-governance, has been relatively slow.

- Inadequate Digital Infrastructure
- Low Levels of Digital Literacy
- Linguistic and Content Barriers
- Insufficient Capacity Building and Technical Support
- Bureaucratic Inertia and Resistance to Change
- Weak Monitoring and Maintenance Mechanisms

- Limited Community Engagement
- Concerns Regarding Data Security and Privacy

Table 2: Digital Literacy indicators in rural and urban Odisha(2023-24)

Indicator	Rural Odisha	Urban Odisha
Households with computer access	1.8%	17.2%
Computer literacy rate	13.4%	25.5%
Internet access in households	5.4%	29.3%
Without Mobile/Internet connectivity	3853 villages	-

Source:

- Government of Odisha. (2024). *Odisha Economic Survey 2023–24* (Chapter 6, Section 6.4.2). Planning & Convergence Department.)
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X. Significance

This research is important because it can influence policy decisions, enhance the quality of life for people living in rural areas, and advance knowledge of the role of e-government in empowering rural communities. E-governance has the potential to empower marginalised communities, increase transparency, and revolutionise the way public services are delivered.

1. **Impact on policy:** The study's conclusions can give government representatives important information when formulating policies. This can direct the creation of strategies and policies to improve the provision of public services and advance rural development.
2. **Bridging the governance gap:** Rural communities experience inefficiency, administrative neglect, and delayed access to government services. E-governance can guarantee that rural residents receive necessary services, expedite administrative procedures, and cut down on bureaucratic hold-ups.

3. **Empower through information access:** Information asymmetry and rural empowerment are closely related. By providing them with various information about programs and grievance procedure, e-governance initiatives such as Common Service Centers (CSCs), online portals, and mobile apps empower citizens.

4. **Empower through information access:** By reducing human discretion and enhancing action traceability, digital platforms lessen the opportunity for corruption and arbitrators. As a result, rural residents have more faith in the governance process.

5. **Localised Implementation and Innovation:** The Odisha government has implemented several initiatives, such as Mo Sarkar, E-panchayat, and Odisha One Portals, which provide distinctive models for localised e-governance practices. Examining these can yield important information about how policies can be modified to accommodate various rural environments.

6. **Socioeconomic Transformation:** E-governance can help reduce poverty, improve livelihoods, and increase the participation of women and underprivileged groups in the development process by lowering transaction costs and making welfare programs easier to access.

XI. Success of E-governance implementation

The e-governance can be successfully kept in view by the following:

1. Create digital literacy and commitment to e-governance
2. Conduct usability surveys to assess the existing e-governance initiatives.
3. Initiating the roll-out of pilot projects and duplicating those that have been successful.
4. Create a national repository of all e-governance initiatives.
5. Create a clearly defined interoperability policy.
6. Regularly and effectively maintain and update the government website.

XII. Conclusion:

E-governance initiatives in Odisha have the potential to enhance governance service delivery and promote rural Empowerment. E-governance has made it easier for rural people to get government services. The goal of e-governance is the ability to access and interact with the world. It aims to provide various online services, bringing financial and digital inclusion in Indian villages and urban areas where the scope is essential. E-governance provides facilities through ICT for a holistic economic and social inclusion model, which ensures the achievement of economic Empowerment, quality of life, and livelihood enhancement. Nowadays, developing countries have the opportunity to better themselves through advanced electronics and more efficient ways to bring the Government closer to the citizens.

XIII. References:

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